

The soil biodiversity and functionality of mediterranean olive groves

Deliverable 2.7: Report on the response of olive grove soils to microplastic contamination. (T2.4)

Microplastic Pollution Report (II)

Date: 31.12.2025

Version: 1.0

Document Information

Project title	The soil biodiversity and functionality of mediterranean olive groves
Project acronym	SOIL O-LIVE
Grant Agreement	101091255
Work Package	WP2
Deliverable number and title	Deliverable 2.7: Report on the response of olive grove soils to microplastic contamination. Microplastic Pollution Report (II)
Deliverable description	Data on response surface design experiments about the effects of increasing microplastic contamination on soil biodiversity
Deliverable type	R-Document, report
Dissemination level	PU
Lead beneficiary	Freie Universität Berlin
Due submission date	31/12/2025
Submission date	4/02/2026

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Document history

Version	Date	Made by	Short Description of Changes
1.0	31/12/2025	Stefanie Maaß	

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1 Introduction

Microplastic pollution has been shown to be one of the most enduring global change factors (Rillig, Kim and Zhu, 2024). Defined as polymers with a diameter smaller than 5mm, microplastic particles can enter agricultural systems via e.g., use of plastic mulch film degradation, application of sewage sludge, but also atmospheric deposition (Tian *et al.*, 2022). In the last years, the knowledge about potential short- and long-term effects has increased a lot. Especially soils were repeatedly reported to be extremely polluted by microplastics which is a direct threat to food production and food security by having impacts on water-holding capacity, soil aggregation but also soil organisms (Lehmann, Fitschen and Rillig, 2019).

As olive production is one of the most significant component of food production in the Mediterranean area (Hernández *et al.*, 2018), it is important to assess the effects that (future) microplastic contamination could have on soil functioning (Rillig, Ingraffia and de Souza Machado, 2017).

In this deliverable, we present the first data on response surface design experiments about the effects of increasing microplastic contamination (up to +1%) on soil biodiversity, soil respiration, organic matter decomposition, as well as mean weight diameter and percentage of water-stable aggregates in olive orchard soils originating from Spain, Portugal, Greece, Italy and Morocco. The end-point of the added microplastic concentration is chosen to be rather high in order to mimic potential future contamination levels.

2 Material & Methods

2.1 Sample Collection

The soil samples were provided by the various project partners, originating from Spain, Portugal, Greece, Marrocco and Italy. The 18 sampled fields can be categorized into one of the three management practices: traditional (TD), organic (ORG), and high density (HD), respectively.

2.2 Laboratory Experiment

All soils were initially sieved to 4mm to remove stones and plant debris.

The water holding capacity was determined to be able to set samples to approx. 55-60% water holding capacity during the experiment.

For each centrifuge tube, we prepared 30g of dry soil. Each sample was mixed individually with the respective amount of microplastic (PE, low density, 500µm size). We had 30 50ml-

centrifuge tubes for each field, ranging from ambient concentration of microplastics (no MP added) up to +1% MP added, divided into regular concentration steps. For each of the tubes, a so-called litter bag was prepared, i.e., a mesh bag with 300mg of green tea. This was weighed prior to putting it centrally into the centrifuge tube with a Hepa-filter lid with the prepared soil. The soil was watered up to approx. 55-60% water holding capacity. The tubes were put into incubators at 20°C for six weeks. Every week, the soil was re-watered to initial water holding capacity if needed.

Soil respiration: To measure the produced amount of CO₂ (in ppm) per hour in each sample, we used a LICOR CO₂ measurement device. Therefore, each tube, now with an airtight lid, was first flushed with CO₂-free air and a baseline measurement was conducted. Then the samples were put back into the incubator for 24h. The CO₂ measurement was then repeated. We then processed these values with the calibration curve to obtain the respective CO₂ value.

Soil biodiversity assessment: After the soil respiration measurement, we put fresh soil samples into cryotubes and keep them at -70°C until further analysis.

The remaining soil was moved into paper bags and dried at 60°C for three days.

Green tea decomposition rate: The litter bag was removed from the centrifuge tube and also dried at 60°C for three days. Remains of soil on the mesh bags were removed before the mesh bag was cut open and the amount of green tea measured. The percentage of loss in weight is used as an indicator of microbial activity.

Mean weight diameter: The dried soil was put into a stack of sieves (4mm, 2mm, 250µm, and 53µm. Additionally, the fraction smaller than 53µm was collected. The soil amount in each of these fractions was weight and then the mean weight diameter (in mm) was calculated using the formula:

$$: MWD = \sum_{i=1}^n X_i W_i$$

Percentage of Water Stable Aggregates (%WSA): 4g of dried soil was used to determine the percentage of water stable aggregates following the respective protocol (Kemper and Rosenau, 1986). The dried soil was watered and placed into a sieving machine. In the machine, the soil samples were moved up and down for five minutes. After sieving, the soil was carefully transferred from the sieved back into weighing boats, dried and weighed. Then, the soil was crushed and rinsed under water. The remaining soil particles were put back into weighing boats, dried and weighed.

3 Results

3.1 Soil respiration

Figure 1 shows the overview of the soil respiration data for each country and the up to three different agricultural intensity types (ORG, TD, HD).

Figure 1: Scatterplots with regression lines and 95% confidence bands for soil respiration (in ppm CO₂ per hour) under increasing microplastic additions (from 0 (ambient) to 1.0%). Data is shown for different management practices (ID) including high density (HD), organic (ORG) and traditional management (TD) and is further separated into facets for each of the five countries of interest (Greece, Italy, Morocco, Portugal and Spain). Note: For Italy and Portugal, only two out of three management practice intensities were available.

There is no clear general trend for soil respiration. However, in Greece, soil respiration shows a clear negative trend with increasing microplastic contamination, whereas soil respiration shows a positive trend in the high density fields.

In Italy and Morocco, the soil originating from the organic management fields, show a slight negative trend, whereas the soils from the other management practices seem not to be affected by microplastic addition. In Spain, the variability of data is very high. In this country, we observe slight positive trends for soil respiration for every management intensity.

In Table 1, we depict the outcome of a mixed-effect model for soil respiration including the added amount of microplastics, the ID (the management intensity) and country. We found significant main effects for management type (p-value = 0.0003013) and country (1.739e-06).

We also found significant interactions between management type : country (p-value = 5.115e.06) and microplastic : management type : country (p-value = 0.0399976).

Table 1: Outcome of mixed-effects model for soil respiration implementing country as random factor and Kenward-Roger's method. "added.MP" = concentration gradient from ambient to max. +1% microplastic addition. "ID" = management intensity, i.e., HD, TD or ORG, , respectively. "country" = Spain, Portugal, Greece, Italy, Morocco. Sums of squares, degrees of freedom and p-values are shown.

	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	NumDF	DenDF	F value	Pr(>F)
added.MP	3293	3293	1	487.0	0.2330	0.6295008
ID	232975	116488	2	487.0	8.2439	0.0003013 ***
country	459639	114910	4	1501.5	8.1320	1.739e-06 ***
added.MP:ID	39080	19540	2	487.0	1.3829	0.2518454
added.MP:country	25216	6304	4	487.0	0.4461	0.7752362
ID:country	504798	84133	6	487.0	5.9541	5.115e-06 ***
added.MP:ID:country	188259	31377	6	487.0	2.2205	0.0399976 *

3.2 Decomposition of green tea

In Fig.2 we present the data for the decomposition of organic matter, i.e., green tea in our study.

Figure 2: Scatterplots with regression lines and 95% confidence bands for green tea decomposition (in %loss) under increasing microplastic additions (from 0 (ambient) to 1.0%). Data is shown for different management practices (ID) including high density (HD), organic (ORG) and traditional management (TD) and is further separated into facets for each of the five countries of interest (Greece, Italy, Morocco, Portugal and Spain). Note: For Italy and Portugal, only two out of three management practice intensities were available.

In general, Greece, Italy and Morocco show higher decomposition rates than Portugal and Spain. In Greece and Italy, the decomposition seems to be negatively affected by increasing microplastic contamination across all management intensities. In Morocco and Portugal, we observe positive trends. In Spain, all three management intensities seem to be affected in a similar way, with organic management being slightly positively correlated to increased microplastic pollution. However, the effects differ depending on country and management intensity, without any generalizable trend.

In Table 2, we depict the outcome of a mixed-effect model for the green tea decomposition including the added amount of microplastics, the ID (the management intensity) and country. We found significant main effects for management type (p-value = 0.0003116) as well as significant interactions between microplastic : country (p-value= 4.570e-05), management type : country (p-value = 1.404e-13) and microplastic : management type : country (p-value = 0.0061194).

Table 2: Outcome of mixed-effects model for green tea decomposition implementing country as random factor and Kenward-Roger's method. "added.MP" = concentration gradient from ambient to max. +1% microplastic addition. "ID" = management intensity, i.e., HD, TD or ORG, respectively. "country" = Spain, Portugal, Greece, Italy, Morocco. Sums of squares, degrees of freedom and p-values are shown.

	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	NumDF	DenDF	F value	Pr(>F)	
added.MP	22.13	22.130	1	487	1.7059	0.1921305	
ID	212.98	106.491	2	487	8.2091	0.0003116	***
country	45.52	11.381	4	5701130	0.8773	0.4764745	
added.MP:ID	32.09	16.046	2	487	1.2369	0.2911824	
added.MP:country	334.91	83.728	4	487	6.4543	4.570e-05	***
ID:country	1006.14	167.690	6	487	12.9267	1.404e-13	***
added.MP:ID:country	237.50	39.583	6	487	3.0513	0.0061194	**

3.3. Mean weight diameter

In Fig. 3, we present the data for the countries, management intensities and the mean weight diameter of the respective soils when exposed to increasing microplastic contamination.

Figure 3: Scatterplots with regression lines and 95% confidence bands for mean weight diameter of soil (in mm) under increasing microplastic additions (from 0 (ambient) to 1.0%). Data is shown for different management practices (ID) including high density (HD), organic (ORG) and traditional management (TD) and is further separated into facets for each of the five countries of interest (Greece, Italy, Morocco, Portugal and Spain). Note: For Italy and Portugal, only two out of three management practice intensities were available.

For mean weight diameter, we observe clear differences depending on the country but also on the management intensity. In most cases, the mean weight diameter decreased with increasing microplastic contamination, however, for example, in Portugal, we observe positive trends. In many cases, there are neutral effects.

For Greece, Italy and Morocco, the different management intensities are clearly separated, however, the biggest mean weight diameters are not always associated with organic management. We cannot draw general conclusions from these data, but have to highlight the variability within the countries.

In Table 3, we depict the outcome of a mixed-effect model for the mean weight diameter including the added amount of microplastics, the ID (the management intensity) and country. We found significant main effects for microplastic addition (p -value=0.03820) as well as management practices (p -value=2.091e-10). We also observe significant interactions between) microplastic : country (p -value= 0.03401), and management type : country (p -value = <2.2e-16).

Table 3: Outcome of mixed-effects model for Mean Weight Diameter implementing country as random factor and Kenward-Roger's method. "added.MP" = concentration gradient from ambient to max. +1% microplastic addition. "ID" = management intensity, i.e., HD, TD or ORG, respectively. "country" = Spain, Portugal, Greece, Italy, Morocco. Sums of squares, degrees of freedom and p-values are shown.

	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	NumDF	DenDF	F value	Pr(>F)
added.MP	0.0555	0.05545	1	487.00	4.3194e+00	0.03820 *
ID	0.5993	0.29963	2	487.00	2.3340e+01	2.091e-10 ***
country	0.2444	0.06109	4	-0.01	4.9637e+10	NaN
added.MP:ID	0.0609	0.03043	2	487.00	2.3700e+00	0.09456 .
added.MP:country	0.1348	0.03371	4	487.00	2.6260e+00	0.03401 *
ID:country	5.5423	0.92372	6	487.00	7.1954e+01	< 2.2e-16 ***
added.MP:ID:country	0.0786	0.01310	6	487.00	1.0208e+00	0.41081

3.4 Water-stable aggregates

In Fig. 4, we present the data for the percentage of water-stable aggregates for the five countries and up to three management intensities.

Figure 4: Scatterplots with regression lines and 95% confidence bands for percentage of water-stable aggregates under increasing microplastic additions (from 0 (ambient) to 1.0%). Data is shown for different management practices (ID) including high density (HD), organic (ORG) and traditional management (TD) and is further separated into facets for each of the five countries of interest (Greece, Italy, Morocco, Portugal and Spain). Note: For Italy and Portugal, only two out of three management practice intensities were available.

Across countries, we find a general positive trend of the percentage of water-stable aggregates with increasing microplastic contamination. Only few agricultural sites are not or

clearly negatively affected, i.e., Portugal-TD, Spain ORG and one of the Spain-HD field sites, respectively. However, the observed effects cannot be generalized to a certain management practice.

In Table 4, we depict the outcome of a mixed-effect model for the percentage of water-stable aggregates including the added amount of microplastics, the ID (the management intensity) and country. For water stable aggregates, we found significant main effects for microplastic addition (p-value=0.002681), management practices (p-value=<2.2e-16) as well as country (p-value = 0.004774). We also observe significant interactions between microplastic : management type (p-value = 0.02701), microplastic : country (p-value= 0.003144), management type : country (p-value = <2.2e-16) as well as between microplastic : management type : country (p-value = 3.388e-06).

Table 4: Outcome of mixed-effects model for Percentage of water-stable aggregates implementing country as random factor and Kenward-Roger's method. "added.MP" = concentration gradient from ambient to max. +1% microplastic addition. "ID" = management intensity, i.e., HD, TD or ORG, respectively. "country" = Spain, Portugal, Greece, Italy, Morocco. Sums of squares, degrees of freedom and p-values are shown.

	Sum Sq	Mean Sq	NumDF	DenDF	F value	Pr(>F)	
added.MP	679.2	679.2	1	487.00	9.1064	0.002681	**
ID	17444.7	8722.3	2	487.00	116.9376	< 2.2e-16	***
country	1124.7	281.2	4	864.97	3.7695	0.004774	**
added.MP:ID	893.0	446.5	2	487.00	5.9864	0.002701	**
added.MP:country	1203.7	300.9	4	487.00	4.0345	0.003144	**
ID:country	10755.7	1792.6	6	487.00	24.0330	< 2.2e-16	***
added.MP:ID:country	2738.4	456.4	6	487.00	6.1188	3.388e-06	***

3.5 Soil biodiversity

We took subsamples for further molecular analyses in order to determine the effects of microplastic additions on the soil biodiversity, however, these data are not yet available.

4 Discussion

In general, we have to conclude that we cannot draw generalizable conclusions from our experiments. For every variable, we find that each of the olive orchards that were part of this study are unique in their reactions to increasing microplastic contamination. Even fields of the same management type in the same country can differ strongly in their response. This leads to the conclusion that the susceptibility of increasing microplastic contamination which we modeled in our experiments, is highly individual for each soil. This is also true for the unique history of each soil, i.e., which management intensity was used before the current one and for how long, which contributes to the observed effects.

In our six weeks experiment, we do not take into account that additives leach out of the microplastic particles with increasing retention time in soils (Rillig *et al.*, 2021) and can provide

a base for biofilms and “plastispheres” (Wang *et al.*, 2025). Though we do see positive trends in some cases of our experiment, this does not mean that in the long-term these effects will persist. It is known that microorganisms can use the easily available carbon from microplastics (Piao, Agyei Boakye and Yao, 2024) and hence might be able to increase soil respiration. However, not all olive orchard plots benefit from increase microplastic addition. We also have to acknowledge that effects will differ also depending on polymer type, particle shape and size, etc. and soils will almost always contain of a mixture of polymers (compare Deliverable 2.6). In our experiment, we only used PE, however, this is the most prominent polymer in the respective agricultural soils according to Deliverable 2.6.

We hence conclude that the effects of increased microplastic contamination will be highly location-specific and cannot be generalized based on our experiments. This is mostly due to the specific soil type and history of land use, but also depend on the characteristics of the polymers.

5 References

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